

Review on Mechanical Characteristics of 304 Stainless Steel using SMAW Welding

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Abstract – *Welding is one of the widely used permanent fastener techniques used for different applications. The welding requires less workspace in industries. In this study we evaluate the effect of the welding process Submerged metal arc welding (SMAW) on 304 Austenitic Stainless steel. The welding process was carried out on 6mm thick plate of 304 Stainless Steel using SMAW method. The plates having the each size of 200mmX150mmX6mm were weld using Tungsten Inert Gas welding. The tensile property, toughness, micro structure and corrosion effect of the welding process of weld joints are studied and compared with properties of process related to the base metal, which shows the better welding process on Stainless Steel. This study indicates that the SMAW joints were having relatively close values, but better strength in the welded joints on 304stainless steel.*

Keywords: *Submerged metal arc welding(SMAW), Mechanical characteristics*

I. Introduction

Welding is a joining process of similar metals but nowadays it is also joined dissimilar metals by the application of heat. Welding can be done with or without the application of pressure and filler materials. While welding the edges of metal pieces either melted or brought to plastic condition and it is used for permanent joints. In all fabrication companies welding is very essential. Since welding has been used in steel fabrication its uses has expanded in other industrial sectors like construction, mechanical and car manufacturing etc. It has been passed through the Bronze Age and the Iron Age and it has branched around the world. Ever since 17th century, after the industrial revolution, technology has made our lives comfortable. Man started using iron and steel and since then they play a crucial role in our day to day lives. There are simply surrounded by metals. Thus it has aided in almost all sectors of our lives. It in the most places, the things are doing or use to accomplish our work. One of the strongest methods of joining any metal is through fusion with the help of Arc welding. Many different energy sources can be used for welding, including gas flame, electric arc, laser, electron beam, friction, and ultra sound. This is related with soldering and brazing, which involve melting a lower melting point material between the workpieces to form a bond between them, without melting the workpieces. Welding is a most careful and precautions are required to avoid burns, part damages, electric shocks, protect from poisonous gases and fumes, and exposure to ultraviolet radiation. Although in its present form it has been used beginning of 20th century but it fast replacing other joining process like riveting and bolting. Presently welding is used extensively for fabrication of different components in automobile bodies, bridges, aircraft frames, chemical plants, nuclear reactors, structural's and earth moving equipments,

railway wagons, pipe and tube fabrication, ship building, general repair works, etc.,. Almost all materials (metals, plastics, ceramics, and composites) can be welded but not by the same process, to achieve the universality a large number of welding and related process have been developed. Most of industrial important processes are classified depending upon the nature of heat source and its movement resulting in spot, seam welds or on the low heat or high heat. Today developments continues to advance of robot welding is common place in industrial setting, and researchers continue to develop new welding methods and gain greater understanding of weld quality. The Most of welding work reviewed in aims at predicting or analyzing the structural response of the welded structure, focusing mainly on the residual stresses and deformations.

I. 1. Submerged Arc welding

Submerged arc welding is a Manual arc welding process that uses a consumable electrode coated in flux. An electric current, either alternating current or direct current, forms electric arc between the electrode and the metals to be joined. As the weld is laid the flux coating of the electrode disintegrates, providing a shielding gas and a layer of slag, both of which protect the weld from contamination until it cools. Because of the versatility of the process and the simplicity of its equipment and operation, shielded metal arc welding is the most commonly used welding process. SMAW also is known as manual metal arc welding (MMA or MMAW) flux shielded arc welding, and stick welding,

SMAW is simply called as arc welding It is one of the methods of fusion welding process of joining two metal pieces by melting their edges by an electric arc between two conductors. The electrode is one conductor and the work piece is another conductor. The electrode and work piece are brought nearer with a small air gap, the gap

should maintaining nearer 3mm approximately. This process extensively applicable for deposit weld metal. This process employs coated or covered electrodes for producing an arc to act as a heat source; the covering on burning provides the necessary shield to protect the molten metal from the effect of oxygen and hydrogen from the surrounding atmosphere. This process popularly known as stick electrode welding or manual metal arc welding and is the single most used welding process in the world. Both AC and DC power can be used equally effectively. About 70% of the heat liberated due to striking of electrons at anode raises the anode temperature to very high values. This heat melts the base metal as well as tip of the electrode in the area surrounding the arc. A weld is formed when the mixture of molten base and electrode metal solidifies in the weld area. Since 70% heat is generated at anode a work piece connected to anode will melt 50% faster as compared to if connected with cathode. This is why work piece is usually made positive and electrode as negative and is termed as straight polarity.

Fig. 1 Principle of SMAW Welding

II. 2. Material selection

The selected material was Stainless steel 304 grade. When austenitic stainless steel joints are employed in cryogenic and corrosive environment the quantity of ferrite in the welds must be minimized or controlled to avoid property degradation during service. Iron and the most common iron alloy, steel, are from a corrosion viewpoint relatively poor materials since they rust in air, corrode in acids and scale in furnace atmospheres. In spite of this there is a group of iron-base alloys, the iron-chromium-nickel alloys known as *stainless steels*, which do not rust in sea water, are resistant to concentrated acids and which do not scale at temperatures up to 1100°C (M. Sharifitabar, 2011). It is this largely unique universal usefulness, in combination with good mechanical properties and manufacturing characteristics, which gives the stainless steels their raison and makes them an indispensable tool for the designer.

The usage of stainless steel is small compared with that of carbon steels but exhibits a steady growth, in contrast to the constructional steels. Stainless steels as a group is perhaps more heterogeneous than the constructional steels, and their properties are in many

cases relatively unfamiliar to the designer. In some ways stainless steels are an unexplored world but to take advantage of these materials will require an increased The materials employed are location dependent in the same structure for effective and economical utilization of the special properties of each material (Andrés R. Galvis, 2011). Only in this way can the designer use most suitable materials for each part of a given structure

II. Experimental Methods

The steel can able to weld in SMAW welding processes which results having different strength. So the effect of SMAW welding process on steel is changes its property. The mechanical property of the weldment of Shielded metal arc welding piece is to be analyze and it has to shows the strengthened value that closer to parent metal property. To determine the micro hardness values of the weldment of shielded metal arc welding piece so as to say the better hardness value by compared to Base metal hardness. Corrosion and micro structure studies are performed on shielded metal arc welding weldments so as is shows the micro structural, corrosion effect of welding.

TABLE I
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF BASE METAL (% BY WEIGHT)

Composition	C	Si	Mn	Cr	S	P	Ni
AISI SS 304	0.06	0.32	1.38	18.4	0.28	0.4	8.17

The mentioned Table 1 and 2 shows the percentage of material composition in weld metal and electrode. The welding of SS304 plates having the dimensions of 200 x 150 x 6mm thickness plates. It is welded by two arc welding processes. Two plates are joined by SMAW simply called as arc welding by using optimal welding parameters. The specimens are machined at 45° angle of each plate and its forming V-groove with 0.5mm weld bead depth for welding. The butt weld type joining process is used to weld the specimen on each welding processes.

The electrode and work piece are brought nearer with a small air gap, the gap should maintaining nearer 3mm approximately. When current is passed, an electric arc is produced between the electrode and the work piece. The electrode and work piece is melted by the arc. In SMAW Welding there are 2 stainless steel plates having the length and width 200mmX150mm and 6mm thick plate. Two plates are joined by Shielded welding process. With having the 45° angle of each plate forming V-groove at 0.5mm . SMAW welding is an electric arc welding process in which the fusion energy is produced by an electric arc burning between the work piece and the tungsten electrode. During the welding process the electrode, the arc and the weld pool are protected against the damaging effects of the atmospheric air by an inert shielding gas. By means of a gas nozzle the shielding gas

is lead to the welding zone where it replaces the atmospheric air.

TABLE 2
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF ELECTRODE METAL (% BY WEIGHT)

Composition	C	Si	Mn	Cr	S	P	Ni
SS E308L	0.01	0.40	1.6	20	0.20	0.4	10

II.1. Welding Parameters

The process parameters for welding process are same for example welding current, arc voltage etc. because of inspection two process of different welding have same parameter and electrode and base metal. The electrode selected for the Shielded metal arc welding is E308L stainless steel material because of 304stainless steel.

TABLE 3
THE SPECIFICATIONS OF A TYPICAL (A.C) TRANSFORMER FOR THE WELDING ARE GIVEN ABOVE

Phase	3phase, 50 cycles/secs.
Current	50 A to 400 A
Open circuit voltage	80 Volts
Efficiency	0.85%
Power factor	0.4
Energy consumption	4Kwh/Kg of Metal deposit.
Welding speed	1 mins/200mm

The electrodes have to prepare slightly high grade for welding. For welding the two different same grades may be not suitable for same grade material so select slightly more grade electrode. The SMAW is the same electrode grade E308L stainless steel used. The welding parameters of each process should same including the electrode, for testing of the welded material with same procedure have to select same material.

III. Results and Discussion

The weld pool is produced depends on the size of the covered electrode and the welding current used and may vary from very small to fairly large sizes. About 70% of the heat liberated due to striking of electrons at anode raises the anode temperature to very high values. This heat melts the base metal as well as tip of the electrode in the area surrounding the arc. The testing result shows that the welding process changes the property of corresponding welding materials.

Fig. 2 Welded specimen

III 1. Tensile Testing

The ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) standards for tensile testing are as per norms of ASTM A 240 on welding work piece. Mainly there are two types of standard dimensions, one for plate and another for rod type specimen. Now the profile is used for welding the plate type specimen. So the selection of standard tensile testing specimen is plate type. The applied tensile load and extension are recorded during the test for the calculation of stress and strain values. The tensile test is known as a basic and universal engineering test to achieve material parameters such as ultimate strength, yield strength, % elongation, % area of reduction and Young's modulus.

Fig. 3 Tensile Testing SMAW Specimen

The testing of base metal tensile property is done and the load value of the base metal at yield and ultimate point is the main factor to be compared with the welded material properties, and the images are shown in Fig 1. It should be less than the base metal properties because heat affected zone is slightly affected on the material property of base metal. The tensile strength of base metal is obtained to be 631 N/mm². This value is the fracture strength of SS304 tested material, so it can be used to compare and evaluate the nearest welding metal property from the base metal. The specimen dimensions of each work plates are nearly same, but the process of welding are different and the tensile testing done. The tensile testing results deviate from the initial stage of the specimen properties.

The tensile strength of welded material decreases up to 50 to 70 N/mm² to the base material strength. The strength of the welded specimen after testing is shown in the below Table 4. The tensile tested specimen dimensions and their load values, strength, percentage of elongation, reduction in cross sectional area of the two

specimens of each process and the average values of SMAW welding of tensile property on stainless steel plate results are also mentioned below. The welding efficiency value of two specimens of each process is calculated and tabulated. The below results shows the difference between tensile property of the welding processes are nearer to the actual or base metal tensile properties, SMAW welding process shows better welding efficiency in tensile testing of the both the specimen.

TABLE 4
TENSILE TESTING SPECIMENS RESULT

Tested Specimen data's	SMAW Specimen1	SMAW Specimen2
Final Specimen Width (mm)	15.54	14.70
Final Specimen Thickness (mm)	4.20	4.40
Final Gauge Length (mm)	70.80	71.00
Final Cross Sectional area (mm)	65.27	64.68
Yield Load (KN)	53.38	52.54
Yield Stress (N/mm ²)	433.98	440.03
Peak Load (mm)	69.00	65.91
Tensile Strength at Ult.,(N/mm ²)	560.98	552.01
Reduction in Area (%)	46.93	45.83
Elongation (%)	41.60	42.00
Welding efficiency (%)	556.49/631.50 = 88.12 %	

The weld ability properties of, namely tensile strength of the Shielded metal arc welded austenitic 304 stainless steel were studied. And it shows the yield strength and ultimate strength of SMAW welding properties were better in that those samples. The ultimate strength of welding having their advantages on that Shielded metal arc method. The fracture strength of two welding relation shows closely related. The SMAW weld plate tensile properties are given Both of the tensile strength below the base metal value but the TIG welding better fracture strength only 5% efficient than SMAW. So the result said that the TIG welding stainless steel 304 grade having the better tensile strength than SMAW welding.

III.2 Impact Testing

Impact testing is the most important testing processes used for finding the joining strength of the welded material. Toughness is a measure of the amount of energy a material can absorb before fracturing. It becomes of engineering importance when the ability of a material to withstand an impact load without fracturing is considered. Impact test conditions were chosen to represent those most severe relative to the potential for fracture, namely, (1) deformation at a relatively low temperature, (2) a high strain rate (i.e., rate of deformation), and (3) a triaxial stress state (which may be introduced by the presence of a notch).

Impact testing is different from tensile testing because in tensile testing the main factor to be considered is %

elongation and in impact testing the main factor is amount of energy absorption. Since the load applied in impact test is spontaneous but in tensile the load applied gradually. In recent days Charpy V-notch test is used universally, so it is considered as the in this work. The material which is selected comes under ASTM A240 (10 x10 x 50mm). For calculating the average value, three weld samples are being tested and the results are shown in the above Table 5. Again the above average results are found to be 18 joule in SMAW welding process and in 16.67 joule in SMAW welding process in charpy testing pointer board, this shows that TIG welding process is the better process for energy absorption welding joints applications.

TABLE 5
IMPACT TESTING SPECIMEN RESULT

Welding process	Charpy impact energy, J		
	Sp.1	Sp.2	Average
SMAW Specimens	18	16	16.67

III 4. Hardness Test

Hardness tests are used to provide generic information on the material properties. Hardness measurements provide indications of metallurgical changes caused by welding, metallurgical variations, and abrupt micro structural discontinuities in weld joints, brittleness, and relative sensitivity to cracking under structural loads. So it is an important property of weld joints which determines the property of rigid, resistant to pressure and not easily to scratches. Here the Vickers hardness test is being implied with an angle of 120° diamond pyramid indenter. The depth or size of the resulting indentation is measured, which in turn is related to a hardness number; the softer the material, the larger and deeper the indentation, and the lower the hardness index number. The three test samples are tested within base metal and weld metal which is shown in the above Table 6. The average value of base metal of weld joints for SMAW is 225 VHN and 214VHN, and the above results shows that the welding process gives better VHN than the base material and also the both processes shows average value of 221VHN. In this work hardness testing results better for weld joints than the base metal.

TABLE 6
HARDNESS RESULTS OF SMAW SPECIMEN

Welding process	Average Base metal VHN value	Weldment VHN value		
		1	2	Average
SMAW Specimen	213.00	214	225	221.00

III 5 Microstructure Study

In tensile testing and impact testing the strength of the weld joints are slightly lower than the base metal. The usage of 308L stainless steel electrode could be the reason for the changes in the solidification of the

weldments, so the micro structure study is made to analyse the phase changes in solidification of the weldments. Etchants are specially formulated for the specific material and evaluation objectives. Etching alters the micro structural features based on composition; stress or crystal structure and it will develop the surface topology.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4 Microstructure view of (a) Weld metal (b) Parent material (c) HAZ

The above Fig. 3 shows the micro structure of the weld metal, parent metal and the Heat affected zone (HAZ) of the welding processes. In the above figure weld metal, parent metal, and HAZ shows ferrite content in austenitic phase in SMAW processes. So in solidification the grains are aligned slightly larger in grain size of both process. Since the grain size is slightly larger there is difference in strength the weldments. If austenite contents present in the weldment it could increase the strength. So to increase the strength pre-heating should be increased upto 10⁰C.

III 6 Corrosion Study

In solidification there are chances for inter granular corrosion in stainless steel welding because the chromium content in top layer will try to escape in solidification, when this occurs oxide formation is possible because of the presence of chromium in stainless steel makes it corrosion resistant material. Oxides formed during welding reduce the corrosion resistance of stainless steels. And through this test amount of corrosion is found and here salt spray test is used for finding the corrosion percentage for about 24 hours as per ASTM B117 standard. The amount of precipitate in liquid using salt spray test is shown in Table 7.

TABLE 7
CORROSION STUDY RESULTS

Sl. No	Requirements	Specifications
1	Distilled water by weight	95 parts
2	Sodium chloride (% by weight)	5 parts
3	Specific gravity of liquid	1.0268 to 1.0413
4	pH (35± 1 ⁰ C)	6.5 to 7.2
5	Temperature	35±3 ⁰ C

The microstructure image shows, presence of delta ferrite in the weld metal has a positive effect on the mechanical behavior of the welded austenitic stainless steels, because it reduces high temperature cracking (solidification and liquation cracking). In salt mist test the sample placed in the salt spray chamber for the following condition as per procedure for both welding specimens given in Table 6. The test results shows after 24 hours, the rust was not formed on the specimen, so the corrosion is not appeared on the three welding media (base metal, weld metal, HAZ).

IV. Conclusion

In the above experimentation results, the mechanical properties, corrosion testing and micro structural characteristics of 304 stainless steel weldments in SMAW welding processes were studied. Results are summarized as follows:

In tensile testing, welding process the tensile strength of base metal is higher than the weldments and SMAW Process is more efficient in these work. In impact testing joints has better impact strength in the SMAW welding joints. In hardness testing, SMAW weldments give same VHN, but strength is higher than the base metal VHN because of the ferrite content present in austenitic phase of the weldments in microstructural images. By salt spray test after 24 hours, the rust was not formed in the specimen, so corrosion is not formed in base metal, weld metal and the heat affected zone in both welding processes.

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